

References

- Büthe, Tim, Alan M. Jacobs, Andrew Bennett, Erik Bleich, Mary Hawkesworth, Kimberly S. Johnson, Kimberly J. Morgan, Sarah Elizabeth Parkinson, Edward Schatz, and Deborah J. Yashar. 2021. Qualitative Transparency Deliberations. Last modified January 2021. <https://www.qualtd.net>
- Elman, Colin, Diana Kapiszewski, Arthur Lupia. 2018. "Transparent Social Inquiry: Implications for Political Science." *Annual Review of Political Science* 21, no. 1 (May): 29–47. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-polisci-091515-025429>.
- Feldman, Shelley, and Linda Shaw. 2019. "The Epistemological and Ethical Challenges of Archiving and Sharing Qualitative Data." *American Behavioral Scientist* 63, no. 6 (May): 699–721. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764218796084>.
- Hall, Peter A. 2016. "Transparency, Research Integrity and Multiple Methods." *Comparative Politics Newsletter* 26, no. 1 (Spring): 28–31. https://www.comparativepoliticsnewsletter.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/2016_spring.pdf
- Jacobs, Alan M., Tim Büthe, Ana Arjona, Leonardo R. Arriola, Eva Bellin, Andrew Bennett, Lisa Björkman, et al. 2021. "The Qualitative Transparency Deliberations: Insights and Implications." *Perspectives on Politics*, 1–38. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1537592720001164>.
- Saunders, Elizabeth. 2014. "Transparency without Tears: A Pragmatic Approach to Transparent Security Studies Research." *Security Studies* 23, no. 4 (December): 689–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09636412.2014.970405>.

Using Pre-Analysis Plans in Qualitative Research

Verónica Pérez Bentancur
Universidad de la República, Uruguay

Rafael Piñeiro Rodríguez
Universidad Católica del Uruguay

Fernando Rosenblatt
Universidad Diego Portales, Chile

Introduction

In the last decade, there has been a significant push for greater transparency in the social sciences. For example, epistemological and methodological debates have addressed the scope, meaning, and appropriateness of research transparency, and scholars have developed tools and practices to facilitate the process. One such approach is preregistration, the practice of recording a priori a study's design and its plan of analysis in open and public repositories (Haven et al. 2020). While it is a standard practice in experimental social science, it has been a matter of contested debate in observational work, both quantitative and qualitative. Arguments in favor of using this practice in qualitative inquiry, as well as opposing views, have recently been published (Büthe et al. 2015; Elman and Kapiszewski 2014; Elman and Lupia 2016; Kern and Gleditsch 2017; Haven et al. 2020; Jacobs et al. 2021; Kapiszewski and Karcher 2020; Moravcsik 2014; Piñeiro and Rosenblatt 2016).

Preregistration serves both the overarching goal of improving research transparency and, in our experience, also improves the research process itself. Regarding the former, preregistration increases the credibility of research because it facilitates the scientific community's access to a researcher's theoretical and methodological decisions (Nosek et al. 2015). Regarding the latter,

preregistration benefits the research process in several ways: it helps one develop parsimonious theories; it encourages one to articulate a clear relationship between theory, hypotheses, and evidence; it improves the dialogue between data and theory; and it fosters efficiency in fieldwork (Pérez Bentancur, Piñeiro Rodríguez, and Rosenblatt 2018b; Piñeiro and Rosenblatt 2016).

A Pre-Analysis Plan (PAP) is one tool that scholars—including those who conduct qualitative inquiry—can use to preregister their research. As defined in Evidence in Governance and Politics (EGAP)'s methods guide on the tool, a PAP is a document that "...formalizes and declares the design and analysis plan for your study. It is written before the analysis is conducted and is generally registered on a third-party website" (Chen and Grady, n.d.). There is no general agreement about what a PAP for qualitative studies (PAP-Q) should contain. There are several general PAP guidelines, models, and templates for preregistering qualitative research (Kern and Gleditsch 2017; Haven et al. 2020; Piñeiro and Rosenblatt 2016). Haven et al. (2020) conducted a study identifying the main sections that scholars who conduct qualitative research in various disciplines should include in a preregistration template. Their findings suggest that a PAP for qualitative studies (PAP-Q) should include four basic categories of information: study information, the

design plan, data collection method, and analysis plan.¹ A PAP-Q further develops a conventional research project. It provides additional specifications of the theory and more details on the methodological design, type of data and its sources, and the probative value of the evidence for assessing each hypothesis.

In this short paper, we explore the practical use of preregistration in qualitative research through detailing the experience of preregistering our study of the origins and reproduction of activism in Uruguay's Frente Amplio (FA, or Broad Front) (Pérez Bentancur, Piñeiro Rodríguez, and Rosenblatt 2020; for the PAP-Q see Piñeiro, Pérez, and Rosenblatt 2016a). We emphasize how the process of drafting a PAP-Q improved the theoretical and analytical quality of our work. We also describe how creating a PAP-Q significantly improved the efficiency of our field research by forcing us to think through the type of evidence necessary to test a given hypothesis or claim. Our contribution to this symposium builds on the results of the Qualitative Transparency Deliberations (QTD), summarized in Jacobs et al. (2021). We also take into account the recommended practices for studies that use process tracing, as outlined by Bennett, Fairfield, and Soifer (2019). Thus, this essay may prove useful to researchers who would like to follow the latter's recommendations in the future.

PAP-Q, Research Transparency and Fieldwork Efficiency

In what follows, we illustrate how we carried out preregistration and used a PAP-Q in our in-depth case study of the reproduction of activism in the FA in Uruguay. In this study, we describe and explain the development and reproduction of the FA as a party with a grassroots structure through which activists regularly engage with the party. The FA is a deviant case that helps explicate the reproduction of activism. We argue that the internal structure of the FA—and the rules that ensure a role for grassroots activists in the highest decision-making bodies of the party—are the product of the extraordinary political conditions that existed at the time of the party's birth in 1971. The intense autonomous activism that occurred during this stage thus acts as an historical cause. Our study shows that the decision-making authority of the grassroots activists, granted incrementally since the FA's foundational stage, enables activists to block changes that reduce their power, engendering a lock-in effect and positive feedback. We show how these rules grant FA activists a significant voice, which imbues activists' participation with a strong sense of efficacy. This perceived efficacy operates as a selective incentive for activists to engage with the party.

We registered a PAP-Q before conducting fieldwork and introduced amendments as our fieldwork proceeded to register updates in our theory and empirical strategy. Thus, preregistration established a “formal beginning of the iteration between theory, evidence, and the interpretation of the evidence” (Piñeiro and Rosenblatt 2016, 788). This PAP-Q covers three of the main dimensions of a study that Jacobs et al. (2021, 176) suggest that scholars should be transparent about: “research goals,” “processes of generating evidence,” and the “analytic processes.”

Our PAP-Q included a theoretical section in which we specified the main concepts and our causal argument. It described in detail the causal mechanisms of the reproduction of activism and the theoretical leverage of the FA (i.e., the FA as a deviant case), as was later recommended by Bennett, Fairfield, and Soifer (2019). The document also specified the empirical strategy and design. It included a set of concrete working hypotheses (both descriptive and causal). Each hypothesis was accompanied by a list of the pieces of evidence required to confirm it, the sources that could provide the needed evidence (e.g., documents, interviews, survey, administrative data, and observation of party's activities), the potential biases in the types of evidence collected. The PAP-Q also stated alternative hypotheses and the related evidence that could challenge our theory. Finally, the PAP-Q contained conventional process-tracing terminology to establish the probative value of each piece of evidence (see Piñeiro, Pérez, and Rosenblatt 2016a, 10-8). Thus, our PAP-Q disclosed our initial research goals, the process we planned to follow to generate the evidence needed to test our hypothesis, and the analytic process that we committed to pursue.

The Benefits of Preregistration for Transparency and the Importance of Flexibility

Preregistering is a way of generating ex ante transparency that improves post hoc transparency. Ex ante transparency refers to clarifying one's theoretical starting point and empirical expectations. This allows readers to trace the research process and to understand the researcher's iteration between theory and fieldwork. It also entails a researcher's commitment to search for a specific set of evidence and its probatory nature. Thus, if the researcher does not find certain evidence mentioned in her preregistered design, or finds evidence that challenges her prior theoretical expectations, the researcher is compelled to explicitly address it. This reduces the moral hazard associated with the temptation to cherry-pick evidence, or engage in ad hoc analyses tied

¹ The template is available at: <https://osf.io/w4ac2>.

to the evidence collected (Jacobs 2020). Preregistering makes post-hoc disclosure of the research process more meaningful as it covers the entire research process and not merely what the researcher decides to disclose at the end of the research.

The qualitative research process implies an iterative process between theory and evidence (Elman and Lupia 2016; Mahoney and Rueschemeyer 2003; Yom 2015). Preregistration in qualitative research needs to take the iterative logic of qualitative research into account. It must allow for the possibility of updating the theory by amending a PAP-Q (Piñeiro and Rosenblatt 2016). In our study, for instance, we amended our theoretical argument in light of evidence collected in our fieldwork and specified the new evidence required to test the amended theory. Specifically, after 22 in-depth interviews and a focus group with party activists, we were able to determine more precisely the role grassroots activists play in the process of building the FA. In one of the amendments (Piñeiro, Pérez, and Rosenblatt 2016b), then, we amended the theory and the hypothesis preregistered in the original PAP-Q, further specifying the components of the causal path between the causes and the dependent variable, and we explained why the changes were introduced.

Given that our PAP-Q included the pieces of evidence, the sources, and the tools to collect the evidence that we had anticipated using, amendments also allowed us to publicly update the evidence or the method of collecting it in response to problems that emerged during fieldwork. In our study, we first planned to conduct a self-administered survey of grassroots activists. We encountered several problems during its implementation and decided to change to an online survey. The online survey allowed us to obtain information not only from activists, but also from party adherents whom we initially had not planned to study and, thus, to collect additional evidence. This change in plans led us to introduce two new amendments to our PAP-Q related to the evidence collected with the survey instrument (Piñeiro, Pérez, and Rosenblatt 2016c, 2016d).

PAP-Qs and their amendments allow readers to understand changes in the research process. This brings more transparency to the research process and promotes understanding of the challenges that emerge during fieldwork, which published papers rarely discuss. In this vein, readers are able to evaluate crucial decisions that the researcher made, and the value of the evidence presented. The disclosure of fieldwork problems and how they were resolved might also be useful to scholars who want to conduct similar empirical strategies. Preregistration serves the goal of improving causal inference through the iteration of theory and fieldwork. The PAP-Q reflects,

in a formal and public document, the natural iterative process of qualitative research, which researchers usually do not explicitly present (Yom 2015).

How Preregistration Benefits Fieldwork Efficiency

PAP-Q not only improves transparency, but also enhances fieldwork efficiency in at least two interrelated dimensions: First, it facilitates the calibration of research instruments, helping authors to maximize their potential to collect relevant data, and, second, it improves the practical organization and planning of fieldwork. As Kapiszewski, MacLean, and Read (2015) note, planning one's fieldwork is essential. Many fieldwork activities constitute a one-shot opportunity to collect evidence (e.g., there may be few opportunities to travel or to interview an important political leader). A PAP-Q provides an opportunity to maximize the results of the fieldwork.

In our study, the PAP-Q prompted us to calibrate our survey and in-depth interview questionnaires so as to ask information directly tied to our outcome of interest. In addition, it helped us to establish the precise requirements of the archival research (e.g., types of documents, availability). Specifically, the PAP-Q encouraged us to thoroughly evaluate the logical validity, measurability, reliability, and the viability of collecting the evidence (both in terms of ethical restrictions and resource limitations).

PAP-Q also guided the organization of our fieldwork. A clear specification of the different tools and the required evidence and sources helped us decide where to invest our scarce resources (both time and money), a critical issue for any scholar, and especially for those of us in the global South. Planning fieldwork entailed preparing a draft list of potential interviewees, checking beforehand the availability of archives (how much was available and the characteristics of the material), and considering other strategies of data gathering. Data gathering has to be planned and prioritized as a function of the probative nature of the evidence that would be collected from the alternative sources (Bennett and Checkel 2015). This is only possible when the researcher articulates beforehand a set of working hypotheses, the possible sources from which information may be gathered, and the probative nature of the evidence to be collected.

Qualitative scholars, especially those who conduct process tracing, usually develop a more or less formal pre-analysis plan of their research before conducting fieldwork. They also transform it during the research process (Kapiszewski, MacLean, and Read 2015). Making this practice public through preregistration incentivizes the adoption of such practices by the academic

community as a whole. For those who usually perform these tasks, preregistration improves the transparency of their work. For those who do not, preregistration forces them to adopt these good practices associated with the research process.

Conclusions and Open Questions

In this brief note, we have presented how preregistering qualitative research improves transparency and the quality of research in general. We have used this practice in various research projects.² We described the contents of a PAP-Q, and how each part promotes different recommended research transparency practices. We believe that preregistering research designs not only improves the transparency of different aspects of the research process, but also promotes greater investment in research design and improves efficiency in the field.

A potential limit to preregistering qualitative research is that preregistering implies some degree of knowledge of the cases to be analyzed. Because scholars who conduct field research often learn a great deal as their work in the field progresses, preregistering a study might entail investigators introducing several amendments to their preregistered plan, increasing the burden on them in the initial phases of the research process. Yet, once the researcher has gained some footing in the study (e.g., after pre-fieldwork) or after finishing fieldwork for one of her cases, she might register the PAP-Q for other cases in which the theory will be tested.

Some authors have raised concerns about employing this practice in qualitative research, ranging from epistemological and methodological critiques to practical considerations. For example, these questions were discussed in the Fall 2018 issue of *Qualitative and Multi-Method Research*, which examined DA-RT guidelines, raised again during the Qualitative Transparency

Deliberations process, and have been summarized by Jacobs et al. (2021). As we have argued elsewhere (Pérez Bentancur, Piñeiro Rodríguez, and Rosenblatt 2018a), preregistration likely would not benefit scholars who work in non-positivist traditions and whose research has different epistemological grounds. Thus, our claims in favor of PAP-Q (cf. Pérez Bentancur, Piñeiro Rodríguez, and Rosenblatt 2018b, Piñeiro and Rosenblatt 2016) do not imply that preregistration should become a hegemonic practice in the discipline. In more positivist work, however, we believe there are clear rebuttals to some of the most common critiques of preregistration in qualitative research.

For instance, one of the most significant methodological critiques of preregistration is that, according to some scholars, preregistration functions as a straitjacket that inhibits potential inductive findings and limits a researcher's creativity. In our experience, preregistration orders what would otherwise be an overwhelming world. It equips researchers to assess discoveries. PAP-Q helps researchers clarify their theoretical and empirical expectations. This, in turn, helps elucidate the value of the emergence of unexpected evidence.

Another critique of preregistration is that excessive research transparency requirements might increase the overall costs of research (Jacobs et al. 2021), creating a barrier for those with fewer financial resources and thereby widening the research gap between scholars from the global North and those in the global South. However, by encouraging researchers to better organize the research process prior to embarking on it, preregistration can actually reduce the costs of fieldwork. In our own case, preregistration made our fieldwork more efficient, which, in turn, helped us use our scarce resources wisely.

References

- Bennett, Andrew, and Jeffrey T Checkel, eds. 2015. *Process Tracing. From Metaphor to Analytic Tool*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Bennett, Andrew, Tasha Fairfield, and Hillel David Soifer. 2019. Comparative Methods and Process Tracing. Report III.1 In *Qualitative Transparency Deliberations. Working Group Final Reports*, edited by American Political Science Association Organized Section for Qualitative and Multi-Method Research. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3333405> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3333405>.
- Büthe, Tim, Alan M. Jacobs, Erik Bleich, Robert Pekkanen, Marc Trachtenberg, Katherine Cramer, Victor Shih, Sarah Elizabeth Parkinson, Elisabeth Jean Wood, Timothy Pachirat, David Romney, Brandon Stewart, Dustin H. Tingley, Andrew Davison, Carsten Q. Schneider, Claudius Wagemann, and Tasha Fairfield. 2015. "Transparency in Qualitative and Multi-Method Research: A Symposium." *Qualitative and Multi-Method Research: Newsletter of the American Political Science Association's QMMR Section* 13, no. 1 (Spring): 2-64.
- Chen, Lula, and Chris Grady. n.d. "10 Things to Know About Pre-Analysis Plans." Evidence in Governance and Politics. Accessed March 3, 2021. <https://egap.org/resource/10-things-to-know-about-pre-analysis-plans/>

² For the sake of brevity, we have discussed only one example. However, we have also used this practice in a study of the determinants of the strength of Freedom of Information oversight institutions in Latin America. For the pre-analysis plan of this study, see Piñeiro et al. 2019.

- Elman, Colin, and Diana Kapiszewski. 2014. "Data Access and Research Transparency in the Qualitative Tradition." *PS: Political Science & Politics* 47, no. 1 (January): 43-7.
- Elman, Colin, and Arthur Lupia. 2016. "DA-RT: Aspirations and Anxieties." *Comparative Politics Newsletter* 26, no. 1 (Spring): 44-52.
- Haven, Tamarinde L., Timothy M. Errington, Kristian Skrede Gleditsch, Leonie van Grootel, Alan M. Jacobs, Florian G. Kern, Rafael Piñeiro, Fernando Rosenblatt, and Lidwine B. Mookink. 2020. "Preregistering Qualitative Research: A Delphi Study." *International Journal of Qualitative Methods* 19 (January): 1-13. doi: 10.1177/1609406920976417.
- Jacobs, Alan. 2020. "Pre-registration and Results-Free Review in Observational and Qualitative Research." In *The Production of Knowledge. Enhancing Progress in Social Science*, edited by Colin Elman, John Gerring, and James Mahoney, 221-64. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Jacobs, Alan M, Tim Büthe, Ana Arjona, Leonardo R. Arriola, Eva Bellin, Andrew Bennett, Lisa Björkman, Erik Bleich, Zachary Elkins, and Tasha Fairfield. 2021. "The Qualitative Transparency Deliberations: Insights and Implications." *Perspectives on Politics* 19, no. 1 (March): 1-38.
- Kapiszewski, Diana, and Sebastian Karcher. 2020. "Transparency in Practice in Qualitative Research." *PS: Political Science & Politics* 54, no. 2 (April): 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1049096520000955>.
- Kapiszewski, Diana, Lauren M. MacLean, and Benjamin L. Read. 2015. *Field Research in Political Science: Practices and Principles*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Kern, Florian G., and Kristian Gleditsch. 2017. "Exploring Pre-registration and Pre-analysis Plans for Qualitative Inference" (working paper, University of Essex). doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14428.69769.
- Mahoney, James, and Dietrich Rueschemeyer. 2003. "Comparative Historical Analysis: Achievements and Agendas." In *Comparative Historical Analysis in the Social Sciences*, edited by James Mahoney and Dietrich Rueschemeyer, 3-40. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Moravcsik, Andrew. 2014. "Transparency: The Revolution in Qualitative Research." *PS: Political Science & Politics* 47 (01):48-53.
- Nosek, Brian A., George Alter, George C. Banks, Denny Borsboom, Sara D. Bowman, Steven J. Breckler, Stuart Buck, Christopher D. Chambers, Gilbert Chin, Garret Christensen, M. Contestabile, A. Dafoe, Eric Eich, Jeremy Freese, R. Glennerster, D. Goroff, Donald P. Green, B. Hesse, M. Humphreys, John Ishiyama, D. Karlan, A. Kraut, A. Lupia, P. Mabry, T. Madon, N. Malhotra, Ecan Mayo-Wilson, M. McNutt, Eduard Miguel, Elizabeth Levy Paluck, Uri Simonsohn, Courtney Soderberg, Barbara A. Spellman, J. Turitto, G. VandenBos, Simine Vazire, Eric-Jan Wagenmakers, R. Wilson, and T. Yarkoni. 2015. "Promoting an Open Research Culture." *Science* 348, no. 6242 (June): 1422-25. doi: 10.1126/science.aab2374.
- Pérez Bentancur, Verónica, Rafael Piñeiro Rodríguez, and Fernando Rosenblatt. 2018a. "A Response to Rosello." *Qualitative and Multi-Method Research* 16, no. 2 (Fall): 42-3.
- Pérez Bentancur, Verónica, Rafael Piñeiro Rodríguez, and Fernando Rosenblatt. 2018b. "Unexplored Advantages of DA-RT for Qualitative Research." *Qualitative and Multi-Method Research* 16, no. 2 (Fall): 31-5. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3524354.
- Pérez Bentancur, Verónica, Rafael Piñeiro Rodríguez, and Fernando Rosenblatt. 2020. *How Party Activism Survives: Uruguay's Frente Amplio*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Piñeiro, Rafael, Paula Muñoz-Chirinos, Fernando Rosenblatt, María Cecilia Rossel, and Fabrizio Scrollini. 2019. "Transparency and Access to Public Information in Chile, Peru, and Uruguay." February 3, 2020. <https://osf.io/n9ef5>.
- Piñeiro, Rafael, Verónica Pérez, and Fernando Rosenblatt. 2016a. "Pre-Analysis Plan: The Broad Front: A Mass-Based Leftist Party in Latin America: History, Organization and Resilience." July 19, 2016. <http://egap.org/registration/1989>.
- Piñeiro, Rafael, Verónica Pérez, and Fernando Rosenblatt. 2016b. "Amendment I Pre-Analysis Plan: The Broad Front: A Mass-Based Leftist Party in Latin America: History, Organization and Resilience." <https://osf.io/zvb9j/>.
- Piñeiro, Rafael, Verónica Pérez, and Fernando Rosenblatt. 2016c. "Amendment II Pre-Analysis Plan: The Broad Front: A Mass-Based Leftist Party in Latin America: History, Organization and Resilience." <https://osf.io/p9nft/>.
- Piñeiro, Rafael, Verónica Pérez, and Fernando Rosenblatt. 2016d. "Amendment III Pre-Analysis Plan: The Broad Front: A Mass-Based Leftist Party in Latin America: History, Organization and Resilience." <https://osf.io/a6n5h/>.
- Piñeiro, Rafael, and Fernando Rosenblatt. 2016. "Pre-Analysis Plans for Qualitative Research." *Revista de Ciencia Política* 36 (3): 785-96.
- Yom, Sean. 2015. "From Methodology to Practice: Inductive Iteration in Comparative Research." *Comparative Political Studies* 48, no. 5 (April):616-44.